

Structure of *Salmalia Malabarica* Gum.* Part I. Nature of Sugars Present and the Structure of Aldobiuronic Acid

S. Bose and A. S. Dutta

Salmalia malabarica gum on complete hydrolysis yields a mixture of L-arabinose, D-galactose, D-galacturonic acid, and possibly rhamnucose (traces). Partial hydrolysis of the gum generates an aldobiuronic acid which has been shown to be 6-O- (β -D-galactopyranosyluronic acid)-D-galactose from methylation studies. Periodate-oxidation experiments indicate the highly branched nature of the gum molecule.

Salmalia malabarica gum, commonly known as 'Semul' gum, occurs in the Indian cotton tree (*Bombax malabaricum* D.C. syn. *Salmalia malabarica* Scott and Endl, Fam. Malvaceae) which grows abundantly in India in wild state. Formation of the gum may be due to some functional disease and generally commences below the bark of the tree¹. It is whitish in appearance, when first exuded, but becomes opaque and darkens to mahogany or blackish colour on drying. Its larger tears are sometimes hollow². Medicinally 'Semul' gum, either alone or mixed with sugar, is used as an astringent in bowel disorders. Its application as a demulcent, haemostatic, tonic, and alterative drug is also known³. The present communication deals with the composition of the *Salmalia malabarica* gum and determination of the structure of the aldobiuronic acid obtained from it by acid hydrolysis.

Crude gum was purified by precipitation from its aqueous acidic solution with ethanol. The process was repeated several times to obtain a sample in the form of white, amorphous powder having negligible ash content. The purified gum on complete acid hydrolysis and subsequent treatment furnished two fractions: Fraction (A), the neutral sugars and Fraction (B), the barium salt of uronic acid. Preliminary paper chromatographic examination of Fraction (A) revealed two strong spots corresponding to arabinose and galactose along with another weak spot, the R_f of which indicated its closeness with rhamnucose. On partition chromatography on a cellulose column, the sugar mixture yielded two crystalline components which were identified as L-arabinose and D-galactose from a measurement of specific rotations and preparation of their characteristic crystalline derivatives. Uronic acid liberated from the barium salt (Fraction B) was identified as D-galacturonic acid from its paper chromatographic examination, basic lead acetate test⁴, and oxidation to mucic acid (m.p. 212°). For further confirmation about its nature, methyl

*XIVth communication on the structure of plant polysaccharides from National Sugar Institute.

1. G. Wett, "Dictionary of the Economic Products of India", Govt. of India Central Printing Office, Calcutta, 1930, p. 487.
2. Howe, "Vegetable Gums and Resins", Chronica Botanica Company, Waltham, Mass., U.S.A., 1949, p. 70.
3. Chopra, Nayar and Chopra, "A Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1956, p. 218.
4. Ehrlich, *Ber.*, 1932, **65**, 352.

ester methyl glycoside of the uronic acid was subjected to reduction with sodium borohydride and acid hydrolysis⁵, when D-galactose was obtained and identified. Quantitative hydrolysis of the gum indicated that D-galactose and L-arabinose were present in the proportion of 2:1.

Purified 'Semul' gum is sparingly soluble in water. Prolonged heating of an aqueous suspension of the gum resulted in liberation of some amount of arabinose. The easy elimination of arabinose units indicated that they might be present in the gum in furanose form⁶. Partial hydrolysis of the gum with 0.2*N* sulphuric acid resulted in the production of L-arabinose, rhamnose, and D-galactose along with an aldobionic acid. This on further hydrolysis with normal sulphuric acid yielded D-galactose and D-galacturonic acid. The structure of the aldobionic acid was finally determined from methylation studies. The fully methylated derivative of aldobionic acid is *laevo*-rotatory and on hydrolysis furnished 2,3,4-trimethyl-D-galactose (I) and 2,3,4-trimethyl-D-galacturonic acid (II) in nearly equal amounts. The former was identified from its crystalline anilide derivative (m.p. 165°) and the identity of the latter was established from its rate of migration on the paper chromatogram and by preparing crystalline methyl 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methylmucate derivative, m. p. 101°. Isolation of compounds (I) and (II) indicates that the D-galacturonic acid is linked through C₆ of D-galactose residue in the aldobionic acid. Hence the aldobionic acid is β-*O*-(β-D-galactopyranosyluronic acid)-galactopyranose (III).

(III)

A number of natural gums and mucilages produce aldobionic acids containing D-galacturonic acid in combination generally with L-rhamnose and occasionally with D-glucose and D-xylose. It is rather interesting to observe that only 'Jeol'^{7,8} and 'Semul' gums give rise to aldobionic acids consisting of D-galacturonic acid and D-galactose, though the position of linkage of the two moieties is different in each case.

Oxidation of the *Salmalia malabarica* gum with sodium metaperiodate gave approximately one mole of formic acid per equivalent of the gum. During this oxidation 7.7 moles of periodate were consumed. Hydrolysis of the periodate-oxidised polysaccharide showed that some of the galactose and a few arabinose units had escaped periodate oxidation. This evidence points out that the gum may be highly branched or may contain a proportion of 1:3 glycosidic linkages or both and that those galactose and arabinose residues, in which branching occurs or which are 1:3 glycosidically linked, remain unaffected during periodate oxidation.

5. Hirst and Perlin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2822.

6. Jones and Smith, "Advances in Carbohydrate Chemistry", Vol. II, Academic Press Inc., New York, 1949, p. 243.

7. Mukherjee and Chakravarti, *this Journal*, 1948, 25, 113.

8. Dhar and Mukherjee, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1959, 18B, 219.

EXPERIMENTAL

Paper chromatographic analysis was carried out by the descending method on Whatman No. 1 filter papers, using non-aqueous phase of any one of the following solvent systems: (A) butanol¹⁰-ethanol-water (5:1:4); (B) butanol¹⁰-acetic acid-water (4:1:5). All specific rotations are equilibrium values and all melting points are uncorrected. Unless otherwise stated, all evaporations were carried out at 40-50° under reduced pressure.

Purification.—The gum nodules (50 g.), ground to a fine powder, were stirred slowly with a 5% aqueous NaOH solution (300 ml) for 6 hours. The red-coloured solution was filtered and the filtrate acidified with HCl to Congo red. The aqueous acidic solution was poured slowly into absolute ethanol (3 litres) with continuous stirring. The precipitated gum, slightly brownish in colour, was collected and the process repeated five times. The final product was washed with absolute ethanol and ether and was dried in vacuum. The pure gum acid (sulphated ash, 0.43%) was obtained as an almost white, amorphous powder (yield 20 g) [pentosans 13.9; pentoses (calc. on the basis of pentosans) 15.89; furfural 8.17%; equivalent weight, 1532]. The gum is sparingly soluble in water and does not reduce Fehling's solution. Nitrogen, sulphur, and halogens were absent.

Autohydrolysis.—A suspension of the gum (5 g.) in water (100 ml) was heated on a boiling water bath for several hours. The hydrolysate was cooled, neutralised with barium hydroxide (excess barium hydroxide removed by passing CO₂), filtered, and the filtrate concentrated. The syrup, thus obtained, was extracted with boiling methanol and the methanolic extract was again concentrated to a syrup. Paper chromatography of this syrup, using solvent (A) as the irrigating solvent and silver nitrate spray reagent, revealed the presence of a single faint spot (*R_f* 0.12) corresponding to arabinose.

Acid Hydrolysis.—The purified polysaccharide (25 g.) was hydrolysed with *N*-H₂SO₄ (500 ml) on a boiling water bath for 30 hours, the course of hydrolysis being followed by iodometric titrations⁹. The hydrolysate was neutralised with barium carbonate, filtered, and evaporated to a brown syrup. It was extracted exhaustively with boiling methanol and the methanolic extract concentrated to a syrup (Fraction A). The amorphous residue (Fraction B) consisting of barium salt of uronic acid, left after methanolic extraction, was washed thoroughly with methanol and dried in vacuum. (Found: Ba, 26.02. Barium hexuronate requires Ba, 26.2%).

Characterisation of the Sugars (Fraction A).—The paper chromatographic analysis of Fraction (A) [solvent (A) and silver nitrate spray reagent] showed the presence of arabinose (strong spot), galactose (strong spot), and possibly rhamnose (weak spot).

Fraction (A) was resolved into its components on a cellulose column¹¹ using butanol¹⁰, half-saturated with water¹¹, as the eluent to yield: (a) L-arabinose, m.p. and mixed m.p. with a known sample, 156°, [α]_D²⁰ + 104° (c, 1.26 in water), *p*-nitro-*N*-phenyl-L-arabinosylamine (prepared by refluxing the sugar with *p*-nitroaniline in methanol and a trace of hydrochloric acid on a water bath for 20 minutes), m.p. and mixed m.p. 202°; (b) D-galactose, m.p. and mixed m.p. with a known sample 167°, [α]_D²⁰ + 82.7° (c, 1.10

9. Bloor and Hutton, *Biochem. J.*, 1920, 14, 754.

10. Hough *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 2511.

11. Charlson *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1955, 269.

in water); methylphenylhydrazone, m.p. and mixed m.p. 182-83°; *p*-nitro-*N*-phenyl-D-galactosylamine, m.p. and mixed m.p. 205°.

Characterisation of the Uronic Acid (Fraction B).—A small portion of the barium salt of the uronic acid was acidified with H_2SO_4 (dil., pH 2) and heated at 80° for 30 minutes. The free uronic acid, on paper chromatographic analysis [solvent (B) and *p*-anisidine phosphate spray reagent¹²], gave a single pink spot (*R_f* 0.14) corresponding to D-galacturonic acid. Under this condition D-glucuronic acid would have given two spots¹³. Fraction (B) also responded to basic lead acetate test for D-galacturonic acid. Barium salt (Fraction B, 0.1 g.) was converted into methyl ester methyl glycoside by refluxing with 4% methanolic HCl (50 ml) for 8 hours. After neutralisation with silver carbonate, the solution was filtered and the filtrate evaporated to dryness. The residue was dissolved in water and treated with sodium borohydride (1 g.) in water (30 ml). After 4 hours, the excess sodium borohydride was removed by addition of dilute acetic acid and the solution deionised by shaking with freshly regenerated Duolite C-25 and A-7 resins. The deionised solution was evaporated to dryness and the residue was hydrolysed with 1.5*N*- H_2SO_4 for 24 hours. The hydrolysate on being worked up left a syrup, the paper chromatographic analysis of which showed presence of galactose only. Another portion of uronic acid (0.2 g.) was treated with 25% HNO_3 (10 ml) in a porcelain basin and evaporated on a water bath to a syrup. This on trituration with 10 ml of water gave a sandy precipitate of mucic acid, m.p. 212°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic sample of mucic acid.

Quantitative Hydrolysis.—The purified gum (0.985 g.) was heated at 95-98° in a sealed tube with 1.5*N*- H_2SO_4 for 30 hours. The seal was then broken and the contents made to 100 ml. A portion of this solution (30 ml) was mixed with D-ribose (0.105 g.), neutralised with barium carbonate, filtered, and the filtrate concentrated to a syrup. It was exhaustively extracted with methanol; the methanolic extract was again concentrated to a syrup. The component sugars of this syrup were separated on paper using solvent (A) and the individual sugars were eluted from the paper strip with water. The sugars were then estimated quantitatively by oxidising with sodium metaperiodate¹⁴ and titrating the liberated formic acid with a standard alkali solution. Galactose and arabinose were found present in a ratio of 2:1.

Isolation and Methylation of the Aldobiuronic Acid.—The aldobiuronic acid was obtained by hydrolysing the *Salmelia malabarica* gum (50 g.) with 0.2*N*- H_2SO_4 (800 ml) for 40 hours. The solution was neutralised with barium carbonate, filtered, and the filtrate concentrated. The concentrate was then passed successively through the columns of freshly regenerated cation-exchange resin Duolite C-25 and anion-exchange resin Duolite A-101 in the acetate form¹⁵ in a slow stream.

After the addition was complete, the columns were washed thoroughly with distilled water till free of sugars. Paper chromatographic examination of the effluent for neutral sugars indicated presence of D-galactose, L-arabinose, and rhamnose. The aldobiuronic acid adsorbed by the anion-exchange resin was eluted with *N*-formic acid

12. Mukherjee and Srivastava, *Nature*, 1952, 169, 330.

13. Gee and McCready, *Anal. Chem.*, 1957, 297.

14. Hirst and Jones, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1859.

15. Srivastava and Adams, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 81, 2409.

solution (2 litres). The formic acid extract was concentrated to yield a residue (5 g.). [Found: Equiv., 352. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{20}O_{12}$: equiv., 356]. Homogeneity of this sample was established from a single spot (R_f 0.058) when examined chromatographically on paper [solvent (B), *p*-anisidine phosphate spray reagent].

Aldobiuronic acid (0.5 g.) on complete hydrolysis with *N*- H_2SO_4 (50 ml) yielded neutral sugar and uronic acid fractions which were identified as D-galactose and D-galacturonic acid respectively by the procedure already described.

To an aqueous solution of aldobiuronic acid (5 g.), neutral dimethyl sulphate (50 ml) was added, followed by an aqueous solution of 30% NaOH (150 ml) added dropwise during 8 hours with stirring. After stirring for another 12 hours, the solution was neutralised with H_2SO_4 and concentrated. The precipitated sodium sulphate was filtered and thoroughly extracted with chloroform. The filtrate and chloroform extract were combined and concentrated. The residue was again methylated using dimethyl sulphate (75 ml) and 30% NaOH (150 ml). The resulting solution was partially neutralised with H_2SO_4 (pH 8.5) and extracted with chloroform to remove non-acidic methylated sugars. The aqueous layer was then acidified (pH 3.4) and extracted with chloroform. The chloroform extract, thus obtained, was distilled to leave a residue (yield 3 g.). This was methylated twice by Purdie's method (yield 2.5 g.), OMe, 46.0%. The product was further methylated twice with Purdie's reagent (yield 2.48 g.; $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 10.7^\circ$; OMe 49.5%).

Hydrolysis of Methyl 6-O-(Methyl-2,3,4-tri-O-methyl-β-D-galactopyranosyluronate)-2,3,4-tri-O-methyl-D-galactopyranoside and Identification of 2,3,4-Tri-O-methyl-D-galactose and 2,3,4-Tri-O-methyl-D-galacturonic Acid.—The fully methylated aldobiuronic acid (2 g.) was hydrolysed with 5% methanolic HCl (80 ml) for 30 hours. Excess methanol was distilled and the concentrate further hydrolysed with aqueous *N*-HCl (80 ml) for 30 hours. The solution was neutralised with silver carbonate and filtered; excess of silver ions was removed from the filtrate by passing H_2S and filtering the silver sulphide precipitate. The filtrate was then aerated to remove H_2S and evaporated to a small volume. The concentrated solution was made alkaline and extracted with chloroform in a liquid-liquid extractor. The chloroform extract consisting of methylated galactose only was evaporated to a syrup (yield 0.43 g.). The aqueous solution left after extraction was acidified with H_2SO_4 and again extracted with chloroform. The chloroform extract now consisting of methylated uronic acid was concentrated to a syrup (yield 0.41 g.) and identified as 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methylgalacturonic acid from its rate of movement (R_f 0.65) on a paper chromatogram (solvent B, *p*-anisidine phosphate spray reagent). The methylated uronic acid was dissolved in water and oxidised with bromine water until non-reducing (2 days at room temp.). After removal of the excess bromine, the solution was neutralised, filtered, and evaporated to dryness. The residue was boiled with 3% methanolic HCl for 15 hours. The reaction product was neutralised with silver carbonate, filtered, and evaporated to leave a residue. This was exhaustively extracted with ether. On concentration, the ether extract yielded crystals of methyl-2,3,4-tri-*O*-methylmucate, m.p. 101° (lit.¹⁶, records m.p. 101°). (Found: OMe, 54.86. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{20}O_8$: OMe, 55.3%).

The methylated sugar syrup (OMe, 40.42. Calc. for trimethylgalactose: OMe, 41.89%) was identified as 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-galactose by preparing its characteristic anilide.

The sugar (0.15 g.) was refluxed with freshly distilled aniline (0.0667 g.) and absolute ethanol (5 ml) for 2 hours. Excess of ethanol was removed by distillation. On cooling, crystals of the anilide separated which was recrystallised from ethanol; m.p. 164° (lit.¹⁷ m.p. 165°).

Periodate Oxidation of the Gum.—(a). To the purified gum (0.119 g.), suspended in water (50 ml), was added sodium metaperiodate (0.539 g.). The mixture was kept in dark at room temperature for 7 days. After removing the excess of periodate with ethylene glycol, the liberated formic acid was titrated against 0.1*N*-NaOH. Formic acid produced per equivalent of the gum was found to be one mole after correction for the titratable acidity of the gum; periodate consumption at this stage was 7.7 moles per equivalent of the gum.

(b). To a suspension of the gum (0.499 g.) in water (50 ml) were added potassium chloride (3 g.) and sodium metaperiodate (1.506 g.). The solution was kept under similar conditions as in the above experiment; 0.5 ml of the solution was removed periodically and after removal of the excess periodate it was titrated against 0.01*N*-NaOH solution, using methyl red as an indicator. After the oxidation was complete (160 hrs), the excess periodate was destroyed by adding ethylene glycol and the inorganic ions removed by dialysis. The dialysed solution was acidified with 1*N*-H₂SO₄ (w.r.t.) and heated on a boiling water bath for 5 hours. The hydrolysate was neutralised, filtered, and concentrated to a syrup. Paper chromatography of the syrup indicated presence of two sugars: D-galactose (strong spot) and L-arabinose (weak spot).

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DEPARTMENT OF ORGANIC CHEMISTRY,
NATIONAL SUGAR INSTITUTE,
KANPUR.

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